

PERFORMANCE OF KANPUR LEATHER EXPORTS, BURDEN OF EXPECTATION & SETBACKS OF REALITY

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Abstract

The leather industry in the Kanpur cluster has long been at a crossroads between increased export aspirations and the government's push for cleaner leather technology; these competing goals frequently cause exporters to be unsure about the leather industry's future. Despite the difficulties, the leather exporter's tenacity remains unwavering. By 2020, the leather industry will be worth USD 9 billion. At about the same time, India produces 13% of the world's leather. Kanpur has always been a top performer, with the potential to produce 2 million employments over the next five years thanks to its specialist saddlery and equestrian products. To comprehend the link between the leather industry's issues and setbacks This research attempts to determine the capacity and expectations connected with leather exports, as well as the problems that exporters face on the ground that prevent them from realizing their full potential.

Key words: Kanpur leather exports, exports challenges, export growth, Kanpur exports growth.

Introduction

Leather is one of the most important sectors in the Indian economy, employing 2.5 million people and contributing US\$6 billion in manufactured goods. The SMEs located in 5 to 6 large sites produce the majority of this output. SIDBI initiated a programme to increase Business Development Services in order to improve the competitiveness and performance of SME clusters (BDS). This initiative, which began in 2006, is co-funded by the UK's Department for International Development (DFID) and Germany's GTZ. As published in (fabrictofashion.com)

Exports of Major Commodity Groups during 2015-16 and 2017-18

Major Commodity Group	Value in billion USD			Percentage share			Percentage Growth	
	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2016-17	2017-18
Leather & Leather Manufactures	5.41	5.17	5.29	2.06	1.87	1.74	-4.48	2.39
Total	262.29	275.85	303.38				Average growth 5.17	Average growth 9.98

dgciskol.gov.in/Annual_Report_2017-2018

At USD 5.3 billion, exports of leather and leather products increased by only 2.4 percent. In the last five years, this sector has remained stagnant, with exports of USD 5 to 6 billion.

Hong Kong was the third most important destination, with exports worth \$14.7 billion in 2017-18. Gems and jewellery products accounted for over 90% of total exports to Hong Kong. The next most important export to this country was finished leathers.

Apart from petroleum products, India's overall exports are made up of nine other categories that account for nearly 80% of the country's total exports. Engineering goods, organic and inorganic chemicals, marine products, rice, RMG of all textiles, gems & jewellery, leather items, medications and pharmaceuticals, and electronic goods are among these categories. (dgciskol.gov.in/Annual_Report_2017-2018)

Highlights of Kanpur leather industry

Key Points	
1. Kanpur specialty	Buffalo leather/ Heavy buffalo processed leather
2. Harness & saddilary	95% share
3. Export share	15% (2003-04)
4. Uttar Pradesh account for	1/3of all India leather trade
5. Industry size	12000cr
6. No of tanneries	400-450
7. Potential of leather Industry	9 billion USD by 2020. 13% of world leather production. Potential to create 2 million jobs in next 5 years. 100% FDI allowed. India is 2nd largest garments producer. Leather and leather products account for 1% of total GDP. Footwear 2% of GDP. Finished leather 14% of total export share (3rd largest). 20000cr of annual worth (Kanpur, Agra, Noida). Employed about a million personal.

Need for study

As a 200 year old industry initially set up by British in India, Indian leather make its place all over the world for its durability and skilled craftsmanship by Indian artisan. Now modern world is looking at Indian market with some revised expectations, with some new markets emerging (Bangladesh leather exports data) and old market stagnating, it's time to look into deeper story of Kanpur leather industry and find the truth between the lines of expectations and reality

Research methodology

This paper heavily rely on secondary data, data from different sources is gathered and compiled to formulate the required conclusion. Kanpur leather sector is a well known leather cluster and council for leather exports as well as other magazines and dally news papers covers its ups and down very closely.

Burdens of expectation by 2020:

1. 12th five year

The Leather Marketing and Export Promotion Scheme will provide a boost of 620 crore to the leather industry for capacity development. The continuance of the Indian Leather Development Program (ILDLP) with an outlay of Rs.990.36 crore has been approved by the Government of India for implementation during the 12th Five Year Plan 2012-2017. As a result, the Integrated Leather Sector Development Scheme (IDLS) provides assistance to all segments of the leather industry in terms of capacity building, technology upgrades, and modernization of production facilities. 30 percent of the cost of plant and machinery for SSI units and 20% for non-SSI firms will be continued with the same amount of financial aid in the 12th Five Year Plan period, subject to a limit of Rs. 2 crores per product line. Investments made on or after January 1, 2011 are eligible for help under the programme. The Government has approved the IDLS Scheme Guidelines for the XII Plan.

The distribution of an investment grant in exceeding of Rs.25 lakhs, previously distributed in four equal annual payments, will now be issued in a single payment under the IDLS scheme approved under the 12th Five Year Plan. The Council had previously requested that the Government provide the grant exceeding Rs.25 lakhs in a single payment, which the Government has now approved. (leatheIndia 2017)

2. Recent foreign exchange expectations

A number of steps are being taken to achieve an 8-10% growth in leather exports over the next two years, an industry body said, stressing the importance of the sector to foreign exchange earnings.

Council for Leather Exports (CLE) is preparing to meet buyer-seller in various countries and to participate in global trade fairs to achieve the target, PR Aqeel Ahmed, its chairman, said. there is a huge potential for this labor intensive sector to earn foreign exchange for the country and create jobs for young people.

Our exports are currently around \$6 billion. In the next two years, the expected growth is 8-10 percent and we have planned several measures for this. Suresh Prabhu, Minister of Trade and Industry, guaranteed full support to achieve this goal, Ahmed told PTI.

He said that in the US, Japan, Latin America, and Russia, as many as ten buyer-seller meetings are scheduled. The members of the council will take part in all big leather trade fairs in countries such as Italy, Germany, Australia and the United States.

In order to improve exports, the trade minister announced Rs 2,600 crore package for the leather sector and the disbursement of money will now begin for infrastructure upgrades and other items, Ahmed said.

"These incentives would help us in attracting investments, push production and create new jobs," Ahmed said the council will also work in Africa and Latin America to explore new markets.

"Peru and Chile hold huge export potential. We are taking our players there to meet businesses of these countries," said the chairman.

Seeking government intervention to address the challenges being faced by the sector, he said unavailability of timely and affordable credit is an important issue which needs urgent attention for the segment.

<u>CATEGORY</u>	<u>APR – MAR</u> 2018-2019	<u>APR – MAR</u> 2019-2020	<u>% VARIATION</u>	<u>% Share</u>
FINISHED LEATHER	721.76	524.15	-27.38%	10.34%
LEATHER FOOTWEAR	2195.54	2081.64	-5.19%	41.05%
FOOTWEAR COMPONENTS	319.10	261.67	-18.00%	5.16%
LEATHER GARMENTS	468.43	429.11	-8.39%	8.46%
LEATHER GOODS	1434.27	1340.56	-6.53%	26.44%
SADDLERY AND HARNESS	159.35	151.44	-4.96%	2.99%
NON-LEATHER FOOTWEAR	392.65	281.97	-28.19%	5.56%
TOTAL	5691.90	5070.55	-10.90%	

Source DGCI & S

In addition, he added, there is a need to concentrate on research and development of new technologies and to attract foreign investment to accelerate the growth of the industry.

Leather is the field in which we import about USD 600 million worth of raw materials per year and use it to export goods worth about USD 6 billion. This implies that in the market, he said, there is a tremendous scope for value addition.

Europe currently accounts for approximately 70 per cent of leather exports from India. Around 42 lakh people work in the industry. (Source PTI)

Leather Export from India

India's leather industry has grown drastically, transforming from a mere raw material supplier to a value-added product exporter.

- During April 2019 to March 2020, the major markets for Indian leather products were US (17.22%), Germany (11.98%), UK (10.43%), Italy (6.33%), and France (5.94%).
- The total leather and leather products export during April 2021 to August 2021 was US\$ 1.65 billion and for the month of August 2021 it was US\$ 385.87 million.
- The total leather and leather products export in FY21 was US\$ 3.30 billion and for the month of March 2021 it was US\$ 317.77 million.

- During April 2021 to July 2021, products exported include leather footwear component (US\$ 77.09 million), leather garments (US\$ 102.06 million), and leather goods (US\$ 357.81 million).
- In FY21, products exported include leather footwear component (US\$ 197.59 million), leather garments (US\$ 295.56 million), and leather goods (US\$ 944.31 million).
- In April 2021, export of leather and leather products stood at US\$ 289.57 million
- India has an abundance of raw materials with access to 20% of world's cattle and buffalo and 11% of the world's goat and sheep population. Globally, India is the 2nd largest producer of Footwear and 2nd largest exporter of Leather Garments. Fifth largest exporter of leather goods & accessories in the world
- The industry is highly labour intensive and employs around 3 million people out of which 30% are women. The sector has a potential to generate 250 jobs for every INR 1 crore investment.
- The major markets for Indian Leather & Leather Products are USA with a share of 17.22%, Germany 11.98%, U.K 10.43%, Italy 6.33%, France 5.94%, Spain 5.01%, Netherlands 3.52%, U.A.E 3.35%, China 2.61%, Hong Kong 2.15%, Belgium 2.21% and Poland 2.11%.
- In terms of volume, India produced 1.8 billion units and is expected to produce almost 3 billion units by 2024 growing at more than 10% annually
- 2.6 bn USD footwear exports, 429 mn USD, 4.42 mn people employed, 524 mn USD Finished leather exports.
- Agra is widely considered as a footwear production center and has around 5500-6500 footwear units including 275 export-oriented units which are engaged in the production of different variety of products. Agra contributes around 65% to country's domestic footwear demand and 28% to total footwear exports from India (1 Make in India shoes to get better, 2015) . It is estimated that around 25% of the Agra's population is directly or indirectly involved in manufacturing of footwear
- Kanpur saddlery was awarded the Geographical Indication Tag (GI) in 2014.

INDIA'S EXPORT OF LEATHER & LEATHER PRODUCTS TO VARIOUS COUNTRIES FOR LAST 5 YEARS.

COUNTRY	<i>(Value in million USD)</i>					
	2015-16	2016-17	2017-18	2018-19	2019-20	%Share of 2019-20
USA	834.10	867.19	847.30	893.68	873.29	17.22%
Germany	674.19	657.37	684.41	659.18	607.44	11.98%
UK	716.49	606.18	616.41	597.30	28.84	10.43%
Italy	407.91	374.09	389.06	368.71	320.75	6.33%
France	308.45	287.74	326.38	323.02	301.07	5.94%
Spain	327.86	293.43	281.30	258.26	254.13	5.01%
U.A.E.	263.15	226.72	161.27	226.18	169.86	3.35%
Netherlands	182.97	169.00	196.98	194.43	178.68	3.52%
Hong Kong	315.26	265.60	248.07	190.31	109.16	2.15%
China	162.21	173.72	170.34	148.21	132.12	2.61%
Poland	65.20	101.06	144.47	115.02	106.78	2.11%
Belgium	84.84	104.90	114.80	114.09	112.16	2.21%
Somalia	100.12	94.12	58.82	102.24	57.94	1.14%
Vietnam	105.54	92.38	104.81	98.44	82.48	1.63%
Australia	84.71	82.66	91.16	95.36	85.15	1.68%
Portugal	62.13	67.61	68.62	68.77	58.38	1.15%
Denmark	76.17	77.22	69.35	67.39	68.36	1.35%
Korea Rep.	82.38	68.65	67.22	66.12	57.32	1.13%
Japan	59.24	63.87	71.42	65.53	59.48	1.17%
Russia	49.01	51.15	56.08	52.59	46.58	0.92%

South Africa	52.87	44.13	43.80	52.28	44.68	0.88%
Chile	52.18	41.85	44.90	48.87	39.97	0.79%
Malaysia	54.58	48.60	48.77	46.32	33.67	0.66%
Austria	26.20	27.86	46.26	43.82	46.00	0.91%
Canada	47.25	46.94	50.50	43.27	47.06	0.93%
Sweden	38.14	40.83	43.20	40.02	34.54	0.68%
Nigeria	17.02	20.29	24.75	37.53	19.26	0.38%
Indonesia	25.62	26.97	33.82	37.23	34.35	0.68%
Mexico	12.49	12.14	19.36	36.07	29.68	0.59%
Saudi Arabia	36.77	40.86	37.87	33.65	38.96	0.77%
Kenya	12.73	30.25	22.04	32.29	16.38	0.32%
Switzerland	29.74	24.83	30.37	31.41	37.17	0.73%
Slovak rep	30.71	31.48	36.44	26.61	20.29	0.40%
Hungary	23.46	28.23	24.65	24.31	20.04	0.40%
Thailand	18.22	19.82	19.82	20.20	16.99	0.34%
Bangladesh	17.66	34.98	27.59	19.84	20.42	0.40%
Finland	16.80	17.25	19.76	18.64	16.32	0.32%
Turkey	27.60	19.96	22.63	16.31	11.30	0.22%
Israel	13.35	13.24	15.87	15.86	17.13	0.34%
Cambodia	12.62	10.37	7.27	10.84	9.07	0.18%
Czech Republic	10.45	9.34	11.91	10.52	11.48	0.23%
Greece	10.95	10.16	10.28	10.46	9.61	0.19%
New Zealand	11.23	9.82	9.88	10.16	8.88	0.18%
Oman	12.76	12.29	9.32	9.46	7.46	0.15%
Sri Lanka Des	13.85	14.42	12.34	9.39	8.60	0.17%
Singapore	23.49	33.04	14.42	9.22	8.71	0.17%
Sudan	20.17	14.63	8.86	9.10	14.11	0.28%
Taiwan	9.87	8.97	8.07	8.44	5.84	0.12%
Norway	12.31	7.54	8.76	6.32	6.77	0.13%
Djibouti	14.79	11.19	8.56	6.28	3.94	0.08%
Others	187.24	209.98	249.40	261.02	221.90	4.38%
Total	5855.06	5646.80	5740.97	5691.00	5070.55	100.00%

Source:
DGCI&S

3. Local business expectations

Manufacturers of leather goods and tanneries in India are worried about the proposal of the new authority. They fear that the cut would create shortages in the domestic supply of raw materials, eventually leading to uncompetitive prices in the global markets for Indian finished goods.

At present, India's net leather and leather goods exports have a very limited share of raw hide and leather skin, a situation mainly explained by higher export duties and strong domestic demand. Nonetheless, the local industry is worried about a measure that will undoubtedly favor organized companies in the tannery market, but could hardly impact the leather sector, narrowing the offer of raw materials (Source worldfootwear.com)

The Council for Leather Exports (CLE) is voicing some of the concerns of the industry: "If leather goods industry does not get raw material, how will it survive and proliferate? Every country preserves its raw material resources, especially in sectors, which are competitive, organized and growing, such as leather in India. Yet, the finance ministry has proposed the export duty cut on hide, which defies logic", was told by a spokesman to the Indian daily newspaper Business Standard. The entity is also concerned that this measure could put India well behind its competitors in the international arena,

namely as "biggest competitor Bangladesh does not allow raw hide shipments and instead provides 20% export duty drawback on finished leather goods" (Source worldfootwear.com)

Setback of reality: set of Challenges faced by Kanpur leather industry

I. Challenges Kanpur leather industry is facing:

Demonetization

Demonetization comes as a surprise to many industries specially industries which are labor oriented and cash does need to change hands to get the work done. As far as leather industry is concerned it is mainly composed of small and medium units where most of the work done by individual worker or a whole family on day to day basis. Cash crunch derived by demonetization created a void in labor market as well as small factory owner, without sufficient cash to pay they are unable to carry out even the most basic functions of manufacturing. The ASSOCHAM analysis pointed out that leather industry in aforementioned centers is facing grave difficulties in production related activities due to demonetization as they are unable to make remunerate on every level of production be it for raw material, for transportation and the workforce. (Economic times demonetization)

Dependency on meat industry Unavailability of hide/beef ban

Leather industry is based on the by-product of meat industry, Crackdown on unlicensed abattoirs, ban on the sale of cattle for slaughter and cow vigilantism together are causing a big slowdown in the meat and leather industry stated (Live Mint Report on Beef Ban).

Much of India's meat and leather trade takes place in the informal economy, meaning the impact of the closing of illegal abattoirs and ban on trading for slaughter is hard to measure. But cattle markets are reporting a big slowdown in trade and tanneries a shortage of hides. Abdul Faheem Qureshi, a representative of India's Muslim Qureshi community of butchers, said in Uttar Pradesh some markets trading 1,000 animals last year were now down to as few as 100 May (2017), the government decreed that animal markets could only trade cow and buffalo for agricultural purposes such as ploughing and dairy production—a move many in the industry say contradicts its plans to grow leather sales. Industry officials said the shock of the ban, coming on the heels of the crackdown on abattoirs and attacks against cattle workers, meant business would not easily recover.

Companies say the government's leather target would be impossible to meet unless the restrictions are reversed. About 30% of hides, mostly from buffaloes, that supply tanneries in the state are from unlicensed abattoirs "More than the economic loss, the government has injected fear," said Chandra Bhan Prasad, a writer and businessman from the Dalit community, as those at the bottom of Hinduism's social hierarchy once called "untouchables" are known. Dalits and Muslims often work in trades that higher-caste Hindus traditionally consider beneath them.

Tannery owner Mohammad Ikram said he was only able to procure 4,000 hides a month—down from 25,000—because even truckers transporting legally obtained cow or buffalo hides fear attacks from vigilantes. He has a month's inventory left, and when that runs out he will have to start shedding staff stated in (NDTV report on cow slaughter)

Infrastructure (CETP)

The Common Effluent Treatment Plant (CETP) is not equipped to deal with chromium. The plant works under capacity due to insufficient money supply from tanners and government. This result in increase in concentrations of chemical constituents beyond their standard levels laid down by government. The chromium released by the tanneries goes untreated to join river Ganga or agricultural land for irrigation

Chrome based tanning

Leather tanneries are the backbone of Kanpur leather industry as Kanpur contributes 3rd largest i.e. 14% of total leather exports in India. However at the brink of sustainable product market schemes

prevalent in global brands, chrome based leather production is gradually losing its shine. International luxury brands like conglomerate Kering has sparked controversy with its desire to put sustainability first and endorse metal-free leather.

A research conducted by online leather product magazine leathermag gathers expert opinion about the use of chrome and whether tanneries are really ready for change (leathermag 2018)

Kanpur based tanners are dealing with this challenge with making tanning as environmentally sustainable as possible, eliminating most of the polluting content in the process of tanning making leather tanning a sustainable process for all supply chain.

Environmental challenges

Kanpur based tanneries regularly accused of polluting holy Ganges river from quite long, however many studies shows paper industry and plastic industry is no less responsible for the same, however leather tanning is a convenient scapegoat for the government wrath. Due to environmental compliances related shutting down of tanneries there are some points worth highlighting.

- More the 250 tanneries have been served with closing order for 4 months from 15/Dec/2018 to 15/Mar/2019 by environmental body UPPCB.
- Due to shutting down of tanneries 90% production related activities has been hampered due to low demand of raw hides in the wake of tanneries ban raw hide price drop from 2000 rupee per hide to 700 rupee per hide as well as some of raw hide suppliers are selling raw hides to Bengal tanners to as low as 500 rupee.
- Estimated loss of 6000 Cr is incurred by leather industry.
- Leather exports have been hampered by 29% from 334 million USD to 237.5 Million USD.
- Continuous struggle by Kanpur tanners has resulted in mass exodus by tanners.

Testing laboratory: Technical Assistance Laboratories

International market is getting well informed day by day, most of the buyers required chrome testing certificate as well as several other certificates when it comes to buying leather and leather related goods from India, however there is very poor infrastructure when it comes to lab testing.

The testing of the leather takes place at Central Leather Research Institute (CLRI), Chennai. Leather samples needs to undergo too many vigorous testing processes and that takes quite a long. Too much time is wasted in getting due clearance. This needs to be minimized (<https://www.thedollarbusiness.com>). Most of the finished leather and leather footwear producing developed as well as developing countries has research and development laboratories and technological testing facilities. It is been found hat either the R & D laboratories or the testing establishments, or both, have pilot tanneries on individual bases without government support in which technological developments are taken a step further towards commercial leather manufacturing by industry. Some of these tanneries have pilot effluent treatment facilities which are leading the way by helping the local industry adopt relevant methods of emission limitation and treatment.

Technical Barriers

By nature, tanners are very conservative. This is not simply inflexibility against change; it is because the quality and nature of leather is prone to change when the parameters of leather processing are altered. Any alteration in the length of processes, process temperatures, float volumes, uptake of chemicals cocktails etc. influence the ultimate character, nature, suppleness, and texture of the leather. Leather being produced from a natural hide which is made up of complex, non-uniform natural protein material, to make quality leather out of it still requires considerable ability and skill in its manufacturing. The adoption environment friendly low waste technology time and again requires a radical modification of most tanning processes while, at the same time, tanners need to ensure that the ultimate product obtained coz of modification retains its marketable properties.

Low waste technologies, in a sense, require better skilled and educated personnel with a sense of environmental responsibility and closer technical control than conventional processing. Thus, unavailability of properly trained staff at various levels remains one of the crucial constraints.

Inadequate Legislation and Lack of Monitoring Facilities:

Pollutant regulation and pollution discharge parameters in most developing countries are by nature rigid and have taken no notice of specific site conditions. Instead of a steady approach as called for which would phase setting up of treatment facilities (for example the physico-chemical followed by biological treatment and appropriate sludge handling process) a tanner is under pressure of environmental institutions to put up a comprehensive treatment system and meet all discharge limitations at once which is outside of his financial and technical abilities. However, very few tanners have the necessary process and effluent treatment control facilities and legislation enforcement agencies usually lack skilled personnel to monitor performance of the installed treatment plants.

Social Barriers

Governments often shy away from dealing with challenges tanners are facing related to modernizing of the tanneries because of the social and even political disruption that would occur. The problem is further aggravated where tanners are traditionally regarded as socially lower because of the nature of their line of work. This group of people, because of their traditional and cultural discrimination, have amassed considerable political privileges. As a result there are difficulties in altering the structure of artisan industry. Same industry such as paper industry plastic industry also contribute significantly in pollution of river water as well as ground water however any at time of desperate environmental measures only leather tanners are targeted cause of nature of their profession.

Slump in UK demand.

“The global slowdown and the weakening of euro as well as Britain exit from European union – Europe alone accounts for a major chunk of Indian leather exports – has led to the fall in exports. The abrupt drop in demand has resulted in accumulation of stocks as importers based in Europe are postponing their due shipments,” (Waki, the dollar business magazine).

II. Conclusion:

This is one paradox – the leather industry. On one end, it is blamed for contaminating rivers and creating health problems, while on the other, its toxicity gives way to purity, and it is heralded as one of leading foreign exchange earners for India and the employment center of about 25 lakh citizens. Seems like odd truths however a reality. And lately, this ‘focus sector’ in the Make in India program seems to be experiencing chill winds from various directions. Will it be too late before the bottom line finally turns red? (Kapoor, Shivani 2015)

In the light of so many disturbances, the policy reforms and incentives provided to the leather exporters come out to be nothing more than a few peanuts. This needs to change if India doesn't want to lose on some valuable export orders.

Without a doubt the leather industry of India has a huge potential to earn truckloads of precious foreign exchange for the country. All the leather industry requires is a little thrust from the policymakers to move in motion by right policies and an infrastructure which is at par with other leather exporting hubs in the world. In a packed out market of foreign labels of luxury leather products, several Indian names have acknowledged their presence on international stage. Isn't this a matter of great pride? And when those concerned with leather industry work hard against odds to make a mark, why should they lose out to the government's apathy? They aren't banking on some divine intervention; all they are asking for is that the government should show some mercy and care for the economic interests of the stakeholders of one of India's prime export sectors.

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